

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D5.6 – Research Design: Public Health Responses - update M28

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Authors	Rut Van Caudenberg, UANTWERPEN Hannah Robinson, UANTWERPEN Lore Van Praag, UANTWERPEN
Contributors	Danka Schmidt, AUTRC Vanessa Moser, SYNIO Rojin Bagheri, SYNIO Zainab Mehdi, TRI Niamh Aspell, TRI Emma Posch, SINUS Henry Polania, SINUS Ilya Sogolov, SINUS Marva Arabatzi, KEMEA Ioannis Bagkatzounis, KEMEA Anna Tsekoura, KEMEA Effrosyni Dima, KEMEA Itamar Laist, MDA Chaim Rafalowski, MDA Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto, FS Dalila Antunes, FS Andreea Furtuna, SNCRR Daniel Modoaca, SNCRR Raluca Buzea, SNCRR Jil Molenaar, UANTWERPEN Isabel Bazaga Fernández, URJC Diego Castellanos Rodríguez, URJC

Roraima Estaba Amaiz, URJC
Francisco Javier Acebedo Esteban, SAMUR
Daniel Muñoz Rodríguez, SAMUR
Paloma Rey Paterna, SAMUR
Maria Herica La Valle, UCSC
Massimo Fantoni, UCSC
Lorenzo Marchesi, UCSC
Gloria Anderson, UCSC
Marina Ghersetti, UGOT
Bengt Johansson, UGOT
Diana Beljaars, SU
Sergei Shubin, SU
Louise Condon, SU

Reviewers

Diotima Bertel, SYNYO
Neda Deneva, SYNYO
Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto, FS

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Executive Summary

The empirical research conducted in the COVINFORM project is centred around assessing COVID-19 impact, response, and lessons learned across diverse local contexts. The empirical research conducted in the context of WP5 specifically aims to explore COVID-19 impact, response and lessons learned from a public health perspective. This report presents deliverable 5.6 (D5.6), which provides a short update of the research design for WP5 (first presented in D5.2 "Research design: Public health responses"). It gives an overview of the WP5-related tasks and activities, and, more specifically on the empirical data collection, focusing particularly on the expert interviews with health care workers and public health policy and decision-makers. The document also includes a brief methodological reflection.

Contents

- Executive Summary 5
- 1 Introduction..... 7
- 2 Overview of WP5 tasks and activities 8
 - 2.1 Overview of WP5 empirical research 9
- 3 Methodological reflections 10
- 4 Conclusions..... 12
- References..... 13

Tables

- Table 1. Overview of WP5 expert interviews 9

1 Introduction

The COVINFORM project examines how vulnerability is defined and addressed in response to the COVID-19 outbreak. The project draws upon complex adaptive systems and intersectional approaches to offer a multilevel and interdisciplinary critique of COVID-19 responses on the levels of government, public health, community, information & communications, as well as resident perspective, and how these responses may exacerbate vulnerability and marginalisation. The project addresses the following top-level research questions, within the target countries and municipalities, across several work packages (see D3.6)¹:

- **RQ1:** How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced?
- **RQ2:** How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- **RQ3:** What were the lived experiences of the pandemic/crisis management within certain vulnerable groups across diverse local contexts?
- **RQ4:** What were the different kinds of barriers and how were they managed?
- **RQ5:** What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

Within this broader context, WP5 analyses COVID-19 impact and response from a public health perspective, with a specific focus on health inequality and vulnerability. The main overarching research questions that have been defined for WP5, are as follows:

- **WP5 RQ1:** How have COVID-19 public health responses been received, implemented, and adapted across diverse local contexts and groups?
- **WP5 RQ2:** How have vulnerabilities and structural health inequalities been addressed and/or exacerbated by COVID-19 public health responses?
- **WP5 RQ3:** How has the COVID-19 pandemic impacted health workers across diverse contexts and care settings?

The research design for the WP5-related empirical research was first defined in D5.2, which lays out the WP5-specific research questions, the study population and sampling, recruitment, and research methods as well as preliminary guidelines for the data analysis and the initial timeline. This deliverable (D5.6) serves as an update of that research design. The document first provides an overview of the WP5-related tasks and activities. Next it will go deeper into the empirical research, focusing particularly on the expert interviews which fed into deliverable D5.3 and D5.4 and will also feed into the upcoming deliverables D5.7 and D5.8. Then, it provides a brief methodological reflection as far as the expert interviews are concerned. The deliverable ends with a concluding section where the main challenges regarding the WP5 empirical research are discussed.

¹ All deliverables that have been finalized and that are mentioned throughout this report are available for download at the project website: <https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/technical-reports/>

2 Overview of WP5 tasks and activities

As mentioned in the introduction, the main objective of **WP5** is to **analyse COVID-19 impacts and responses from a public health perspective**, with a specific focus on **health inequality and vulnerability**.

WP5 consists of four tasks, which are conducted in two iterations resulting in two deliverables per task. **Task 5.1** aimed to describe **public health systems and responses** to the COVID-19 pandemic across the COVINFORM partner countries using a comprehensive desk-based approach. This has resulted in two Baseline Reports: D5.1 (June 2021) and D5.5 (September 2022). The first Baseline Report (D5.1) tackles a wide range of subtopics within the broader theme of public health responses and provides a comprehensive insight in key similarities and divergences in various dimensions of public health responses to the COVID-19 pandemic across COVINFORM partner countries. The second Baseline Report (D5.5) takes a more focused approach and specifically looks at the COVINFORM partner countries' pandemic preparedness plans and evaluations of specific public health responses. **Task 5.2** revolves around conducting the **empirical research**. This task includes the research design outlined in deliverable D5.2 (October 2021) with the aim to guide and streamline the WP5-related empirical activities. The empirical data collection for WP5 consists of expert interviews with health care workers and public health policy- and decision-makers in ten COVINFORM partner countries (see further for more details) as well as resident interviews in each of those research sites (for more information about the resident interviews, see D3.3 and D3.6 from WP3). The current deliverable D5.6 (February 2023) provides a brief update of the research design, including some methodological reflections on the data collection regarding the expert interviews.

The aim of the empirical research conducted in the context of Task 5.2 is to explore **COVID-19 public health responses and their impact through an in-depth analysis of first-hand lived experiences and various stakeholders' personal and professional insights**. The purpose is to gain a greater understanding of decision-making processes during the COVID-19 pandemic and to shed light on the impacts experienced by practitioners and residents in ten partner countries, i.e. Austria, Belgium, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Germany, Wales and England. Moreover, the intention is to elucidate good practices and lessons learned. These activities are part of Task 5.3 and Task 5.4. More specifically, **Task 5.3** focuses on the **analysis of the empirical data** collected in Task 5.2. Preliminary findings of the expert interviews are discussed in D5.3 (March 2022), which consists of four thematic chapters written by various COVINFORM partners. Within the broader theme of public health responses, these chapters tackle the following issues: i) comparative definitions and operationalization of health vulnerabilities, ii) institutional, legal, and data collection factors influencing public health responses, iii) communication around vaccines and vaccination campaigns, and iv) impacts of COVID-19 on health care workers. A further analysis of the expert interviews from each of the ten research sites will feed into deliverable D5.7 (July 2023). Finally, **Task 5.4 synthesises and interprets WP5-related research findings**. In deliverable D5.4 (May 2022), the preliminary findings of the expert interviews are synthesized and illuminate decision-making processes during the COVID-19 pandemic as well as the impact of the pandemic on public health practitioners and policymakers in the ten COVINFORM partner countries. Deliverable D5.8 (September 2023) will be the final deliverable of WP5 and will include best practices and lessons learned based on the research findings.

In the following section, we focus on the WP5-related empirical research activities. We provide a brief overview of the empirical research with an update on the data that has been collected so far as well as pending empirical activities.

2.1 Overview of WP5 empirical research

Based on the preliminary findings of WP5 and in line with the project's top-level research questions mentioned at the beginning of this report, the research questions that will guide the analysis and interpretation of WP5 findings for the upcoming deliverables D5.7 and D5.8 have been refined as follows:

- RQ1: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced?
- RQ2: How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- RQ3: What were the lived experiences of the pandemic and its response within certain vulnerable groups?
- RQ4: What were the different kinds of barriers and how were they managed?
- RQ5: What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

The empirical data that contribute to answering these research questions are qualitative and consist of semi-structured expert interviews with health care workers and public health policy- and decision-makers, as well as semi-structured interviews with residents, focusing particularly on women of low socio-economic status as these are exposed to multiple vulnerabilities through their gender and SES. As mentioned, this deliverable reports solely on the expert interviews (for the resident interviews, see D3.2 and D3.6). For the interviews with health care workers, partners were encouraged to focus on General Practitioners (GPs) or 'family doctors' (medico di base/famiglia; Hausarzt; clínico geral; médico general; husläkare; huisarts, etc.). For the interviews with public health policy- and decision-makers, partners were encouraged to focus on individuals working at the national public health institute and/or people in a coordination/leadership position for the implementation of vaccination campaigns. The latter category could also be people leading vaccination campaigns at the local level (e.g., at the level of a city or region). The specific questions and topic guides for the interviews and the analysis for these two populations of interest can be found in the initial research design D5.2.

Regarding these WP5 expert interviews, the objective was to conduct at least 5 interviews (ideally $n \geq 3$ health care workers and $n \geq 2$ public health policy- and decision-makers) in each of the ten research sites. The expert interviews were conducted between October 2020-March 2021, a time during which health care workers and public health policy and decision-makers were extremely busy, given the situation of the pandemic. This complicated data collection and resulted in the fact that the target number could not be reached in all research sites. As detailed in Table 1, at the time of writing this report a total of 48 interviews were conducted across the ten target countries.

Table 1. Overview of WP5 expert interviews

Partner	Research site	Number of interviews with HCWs	Number of interviews with PHDMs	Total number of expert interviews
SYNYO	Austria	0	4	4 completed interviews – 1 pending
UANTWERPEN	Belgium	3	2	5 completed interviews

KEMEA	Greece	3	2	5 completed interviews
UCSC; SAPIENZA	Italy	3	2	5 completed interviews
FS	Portugal	4	1	5 completed interviews
URJC	Spain	3	2	5 completed interviews
UGOT	Sweden	3	4	7 completed interviews
SU	Wales	3	3	6 completed interviews
SINUS	Germany	4	0	4 completed interview – 1 pending
TRI	England	0	2	2 completed interviews – 3 pending
Total		26	22	48 completed interviews – 5 pending

In order to address the low response rate in some of the target countries during the initial data collection period that resulted in the preliminary findings of D5.3 and D5.4, partners can continue conducting expert interviews to reach the target of n=5 until mid-April 2023. This will allow for a more complete data set for the analysis for the upcoming deliverables D5.7 and D5.8. Still, given the qualitative nature of the data and the overall small sample – even in case it is complete –, it is important to note that the purpose of the empirical research is not to make generalizing claims about a specific research site. Rather, the healthcare workers and public health policy- and decision-makers expert interviews will be used to highlight the process of decision making and to explore how public health measures affected, ignored, or were adapted for different vulnerable groups across the different research sites.

3 Methodological reflections

Empirical research presented in deliverables across WP4-7 has been analysed according to the themes of their WPs and the research teams' expertise. Additionally, there is a common framework for analysis spanning all for WPs and domains. This enables the COVINFORM project to discuss findings across WPs.

For WP5 specifically, COVINFORM partners used expert purposive sampling (Palinkas et al., 2015) and relied mostly on publicly available contact details to select individuals based on their profession. Once the first experts were recruited, snowball sampling was also used for further recruitment. All interviews were in line with GDPR guidelines. As mentioned, the WP5 expert interviews were semi-structured interviews. To structure the interviews and to ensure similar data would be collected across the research sites, UANTWERPEN provided partners with topic guides (see Appendix 1 in D5.2). The topic guides were guided by the specific questions for health care workers and for public health policy and decision-makers mentioned in the section above. The topic guides consisted of different groups of questions, including 'probes' which encourage participants to elaborate on a point or provide additional information. The topic guides were relatively structured, so that research results can be compared across the consortium. However, the questions were quite open in nature, to allow participants freedom in their responses and to avoid only finding 'what is expected' (Devers & Frankel, 2000). The topic guides were provided in English and were translated to the necessary language(s) by the partners themselves. The interviews generally lasted between 1 and 1.5 hours. All interviews were audio recorded, pseudonymized, and carefully transcribed ad verbatim, to serve as a basis for

systematic thematic analyses (Clarke, Braun & Hayfield, 2015). To ensure systematic analysis, data and researcher triangulation was applied and all interpretations were double-checked with the interviewers and COVINFORM partners. For D5.4, interview quotes were, after translation to English, sometimes revised to facilitate reading and understanding.

Challenges that partners encountered during the research were related to the chosen target site and the recruitment of health care workers and public health policy and decision-makers. Although this may apply to many groups that we aim to reach during the COVINFORM project, the specific target groups and sites for this WP were particularly difficult to reach. This is because they are seen as primarily professional actors with disproportionately high work load during and after the pandemic and were also especially vulnerable to being infected with the COVID-19 virus. Furthermore, despite the disproportional impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on their professional lives, which also impacted other life spheres, they were in many cases not rewarded proportionally – in terms of working conditions and financial rewards. This also impacted their reachability. This was particularly the case as recruitment took place during the winter period of 2020-2021, when COVID-19 rates were high and it was challenging to find the time to conduct interviews. Many interviews had to be rescheduled due to pandemic-related matters and the ongoing heavy workload of many health professionals. At the same time, those who participated could use this interview to reflect on this burden throughout the pandemic. Given the circumstances, considerable flexibility was shown in terms of rescheduling interviews, interview locations, and interviews being conducted virtually.

As a final note, more free responses in terms of critique on their institution and less perspectives from their colleagues or people who worked in a comparable setting could have been of added value to assess the data. Since some partners selected healthcare workers for their case study, this will also allow to delve more in the difficulties these professions had to face, as well as to assess to assess their experiences more properly (see WP3 for more details).

As mentioned, preliminary analysis of the empirical material gathered via the expert interviews has been conducted for deliverables D5.3 and D5.4. Further analysis will feed into the upcoming deliverables D5.7 and D5.8. The analyses for these two deliverables will be based on a project-wide approach based on a framework developed by the project leader SYNYO and project partner FS. For D5.7, the empirical material will be organized following the established frames in the context of the socio-ecological systems approach. The deliverable will also include a short section for each country containing a descriptive and analytical part. The expert interviews will be used to enrich the analysis of how the public health responses were designed and implemented and how vulnerable groups were affected. The analysis will differentiate between official documents and the experts' opinions. Interviews with healthcare professionals will be used to analyse, for instance, how measures affected their patients. In addition, in a separate section, healthcare workers' interviews will be used to illustrate the effects the pandemic had on their own professional and personal lives.

For D5.8, the country profiles from D5.7. will be used for the synthesis. A typology of health responses and measures will be created. Best practices and lessons learned will be drafted, based on this typology and, when possible, on the comparisons between the different country cases.

4 Conclusions

In this deliverable, we presented an update of the WP5 research design initially described in D5.2 with the aim to streamline the WP5-related empirical research across the different research sites and to provide a clear set of expectations and guidelines. This update gives an overview of the WP5-related tasks and activities and, more specifically, of the data collection that has been carried out, focusing particularly on the expert interviews. This update comes after preliminary analyses of the expert interviews regarding public health responses (see D5.3 and D5.4) and precedes further analyses that will feed into the upcoming deliverables D5.7 and D5.8.

The overview of empirical research and methodological reflections of this deliverable, show that the main challenges with carrying out the empirical research relate to the difficulties to find public health experts available and willing to participate in an interview in the midst of a pandemic that put them under a great amount of stress and burdened them with a heavy workload. To address this issue of missing data, partners who have had the most difficulties in recruiting experts during the initial round of data collection are therefore encouraged to make additional efforts to increase their sample of expert interviews. This will allow to enrich the sample for the remaining WP5-related analytic work with more expert voices that can help us reveal best practices and lessons learned when it comes to public health responses.

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